

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: RAUM****FIRST NAME: DOMINIQUE****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2019, Grammarly v.1.0.32.485 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Kate Turabian identified several actions that are at risk of being seen as plagiarism and need referencing. (Select all that apply).
 - You quote, paraphrase or summarise a source but fail to cite it.**¹
 - You use ideas or methods from a source but fail to cite them.**²
 - You use the exact words of a source, and you do cite it but fail to put those words in question marks or in a block quotation.**³
 - You paraphrase a source and mention it but paraphrase too closely.**⁴

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition (Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 80.

² Turabian, Kate L., 80.

³ Turabian, Kate L., 80.

⁴ Turabian, Kate L., 80.

2. When applying the Chicago style of referencing, you may choose to (select all that apply):
- Place the author’s name, date, and page numbers between parentheses using the author-date type.**⁵
 - Place the author’s name, surname, date and page number between parentheses using the author-date style.
 - Use numerical footnotes as a link to the reference in the bibliography.
 - Use a shorter format using the name, followed by the source’s title and the page references, when reusing a source mentioned before while using the note style.**⁶
3. Which of the following contents are not part of the “prebuild” before the introduction?
- Limitations and delimitations.**⁷
 - The abstract.
 - The copyright.
 - Dedications and acknowledgements.
4. When applying the World Health Organization (WHO) style to the bibliography of a research paper, the following rules apply (check the correct answer):
- References are to be listed in order of appearance in the paper.

⁵ Turabian, Kate L., 142.

⁶ Turabian, Kate L., 141-142.

⁷ Turabian, Kate L., 67-70.

- Only the first author is to be mentioned. The following ones will be replaced by mentioning “et al.”.
 - When writing technical documents, the author must provide references with a superscript number, with all data given at the bottom of the page in numerical order throughout the piece.⁸**
 - None of the above applies.
5. When using the World Health Organization (WHO) style, quotations (check the correct answer):
- Are to be adapted to the spelling and grammar of the English language used (United Kingdom or United States).
 - Punctuations should be enclosed inside the quotation marks if they are part of the quotation, even if using United States grammar.⁹**
 - Punctuations should always be enclosed inside the quotation marks, even if using United States grammar.
 - Need to be written in italic and bold format and placed between double quotes.
6. The qualitative research approach should not be used when (check the correct answer):
- When explaining a process or behaviour.
 - When understanding a phenomenon, a case, a behaviour or a situation.

⁸ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*. Second edition (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 36.

⁹ World Health Organization, 51.

- When describing an issue using numerical data.**¹⁰
- When collecting participants' stories, retell them to address the research question.
7. The conclusion of a research paper will include (check the correct answer):
- Final reflections.
- A conclusion to every finding.
- A presentation of actionable recommendations.
- All of the above.**¹¹
8. The basics of paper writing at Euclid University include the following rules (check the correct answer):
- Abbreviations should solely be used between parenthesis and are to be avoided in the main text.**¹²
- Abbreviations can be used as long as there is a list of acronyms and a first usage of the entire word with the abbreviation in parenthesis following.
- The referencing style (Chicago, WHO or APA) is up to the student but has to be mentioned and be consistent.
- The student has to use in-text referencing in every type of paper.

¹⁰ Adu, Philip, *Writing the methodology chapter of a qualitative study*, YouTube Video, 2016, 1:49 to 3:01, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708&pp=ygU2V3JpdGluZyB0aGUGbWV0aG9kb2xvZ3kgY2hhcHRlciBvZiBhIHh1YWxpZGF0aXZlIHNoZWV0>

¹¹ Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe, 679-683.

¹² Cleenewerck Laurent and Gulma Kabiru, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021). 40.

9. Which of the following is not part of qualitative research? (Check the correct answer).

- Description of data collection methods or tools.
- Ethical considerations.
- Issues of trustworthiness.
- Calculation of the plagiarism percentage.**¹³

10. When proceeding to the analysis, interpretation, and synthesis of findings, the following points need to be respected (check the correct answer):

- The collected data has to be presented understandably; inconsistent or unexpected data should be ignored.
- The collected data has to be presented understandably; inconsistent or unexpected data should not be ignored or deleted.**¹⁴
- The collected data has to be presented understandably; inconsistent or unexpected data should be deleted.
- The collected data does not have to be presented understandably; but needs to be consistent.

¹³ Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe, 435-438.

¹⁴ Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe, 83-84.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Adu, Philip. *Writing the methodology chapter of a qualitative study*, 2016. YouTube Video. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708&pp=ygU2V3JpdGluZyB0aGUgbWV0aG9kb2xvZ3kgY2hhcHRlciBvZiBhIHF1YWxp dGF0aXZlIHNo dWR5>.

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Incorporated, 2019.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.